

Feasibility Study of a Solar Carport System in the Parking Area of Factory in New Valley Governorate; Connected to the Grid

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Abstract

Solar electricity is an important factor for future energy sustainability. As the world's population grows, so does the demand for energy. Solar energy is one of the most promising sustainable energy sources that are developing quickly. The advantages of solar-powered parking solutions will be covered in the current research paper, along with some of their key characteristics. Technical and financial viability of installing a solar power generation system in the rear parking lot of a factory in Egypt's New Valley Governorate are covered in this paper. This study assesses solar energy's potential as a sustainable solution in light of growing energy demands and a dedication to lowering carbon footprints. This study evaluates the performance of the suggested solar power generation system using PVSyst simulation. According to the simulation results, the crystal module has a 610 watt rated power and is of the Jinko JKM-610N-78HL4-BDV brand. The total output of the 1872 PV modules in the solar parking lot is 924 kW ac, with 760 V and 1390 A. Eight inverters and three boosters connect these groups to the grid. This proposed facility has 1142 kWp of total electricity. An annual total of 2211.5 megawatt hours of generated electricity were supplied to the system. The advantages of solar-powered parking solutions; that include lowering carbon footprint, will be covered in this article, along with some of their key characteristics. Technical and financial viability of installing a solar power generation system in the parking lot of a factory in New Valley Governorate; Egypt, are also stated.

Keywords: Car Parking; Solar Energy; Feasibility Study; PVSyst; Electricity; Carbon emission

1. Introduction

The market for automated parking systems is expanding due to a number of factors, including the growing number of cars, the lack of parking space, urbanization, and the growing need for sustainable and green parking options. These solutions provide a more efficient, user-friendly experience, and eliminate the need for large parking lots by optimizing the parking capacity. Another significant element driving the market's expansion is the ongoing development of robotics and artificial intelligence (AI). Parking operations are made safer, more accurate, and more efficient by this technology. Parking system scheme is shown in figure 1 [1] and an automated parking snapshot is presented in figure 2 [3]. Figure 3 illustrates the market size of automated parking system [4]. There are 435 thousand of public garages in Egypt, with 232 thousand located in rural areas and 203 thousand in urban areas, according to data from the Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics, as depicted in figure 4 [5]. At the moment, the majority of these garages are either closed or utilized for other business purposes. Egypt spends LE 50 billion (\$8 billion) annually on traffic congestion, which is 4% of GDP (gross domestic product).

Fig.1: Parking System Scheme [1]

Fig.2: Automated parking snapshot [3]

The maximum capacity of an automated parking system is significantly influenced by the type that is used. For instance, tower systems are perfect for tiny urban areas since they can stack cars vertically. Carousel systems, on the other hand, house automobiles in a circular structure to enhance efficiency. Compared to conventional parking garages, both solutions enable parking facilities to accommodate a significantly larger number of automobiles. When mechanical parking systems are taken into consideration, the capacity disparity becomes much more noticeable. By Removing ramps and walkways and automating the vehicle retrieval procedure, mechanical solutions boost parking density. A mechanical device called the SMART parking system was created to lessen the amount of space or volume needed for parking. It offers parking for cars on several levels that are piled vertically. Instead of the driver, it transports cars to and from parking spots. This solution is environmentally beneficial since it lowers dangerous pollutants while people are waiting in line. The SPV-Roxy Parking Co., which uses Korean technology to build Egypt's first automated parking lot, is currently owned by Smart Parking, which is targeting to be the top supplier of automated parking solutions in Egypt and the MENA area. To own all of the tools and supplies needed, the company teamed up with Switzerland and Korean suppliers.

Fig.3: Automated parking system market size [4]

Fig. 4: Percentage of available Garages in Egyptian cities to the total number of available Garages in Egypt [5]

Solar energy is becoming more popular for parking options. Solar-powered parking solutions come in a variety of forms. One excellent option to manage one or more parking bays is with the solar-powered remote-control parking bay barrier. Installing solar panels above the parking lot serves several purposes. Solar-powered parking lot shade structures are a great way to use the sun's energy, money savers, and support sustainability. Hence, this solution helps saving energy expenses while also increasing employee or customer comfort. Solar carport scheme is shown in figure 5 [6]. The benefits of solar carport are:

- Use of renewable energy help maintaining cleaner environment
- Enhance sustainability
- Lower traditional energy expenses.
- Solar-powered parking would help achieving energy independency

Incorporating solar power into a parking facility has several benefits such as cooling different vehicles, and surrounding area, in addition to using solar energy to generate electricity. This type

of parking garage has solar panels attached to a supporting structure. Larger solar energy generation from panels' surface lowers on-grid power usage.

Fig.5: Solar Carport parking scheme[6]

From 2023 to 2030, the global solar carport market is expected to expand at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.9%, from its projected USD 458.7 million in 2022. The market for solar carports is expanding due to the growing need for environment friendly mobility and the growing need for sustainable renewable energy sources. The market size of solar carport is illustrated in figure 6 [7]. Percent of solar carport market size by vehicle arrangement in 2023 chart is presented in figure 7 [8], while global solar carport market size by application is exhibited in figure 8 [9].

Fig.6:Solar carport market size[7]

Fig.7: Percent of Solar carport market size by vehicle arrangement, 2023 [8]

Fig.8: Global solar carport market size by application and forecast [9]

2. Previous Work

Compared to other renewable energy uses in power networks, the potential for large-scale integration of solar photovoltaic (PV) systems has not been thoroughly investigated. Building or installing parking lots with solar PV systems installed on their rooftops is one of the suggested strategies for the sustainable integration of EVs with solar energy in electricity systems. Given that research indicates that EVs remain parked for the great majority of the time, this idea improves the power system's robustness and dependability. In a study by Osório et al. [10] a thorough analysis of the most recent developments in photovoltaic (PV) panels, electric vehicles (EVs), and batteries was presented. In another study [11], the efficiency of an off-grid solar photovoltaic system for EV charging in a long-term parking lot was examined. Analyzing the state of charge (SoC) at departure of EVs plugged in at the parking lot during the simulated year, the efficacy of charging was examined. Even if only a tiny percentage of cars leave with insufficient charge throughout the year, this percentage rises significantly during winter months when there is less light. Enhancing charging adequacy can be achieved by increasing the system's solar modules' efficiency and the amount of time spent in the parking lot.

One significant way to support carbon neutrality and net zero emissions in transportation systems is to integrate photovoltaic into urban bus parking spaces. However, Photovoltaic bus parking lots didn't receive enough attention till now, with the exception of some studies on their integration with bus roofs and parking lots. A number of researchers presented a novel approach [12] to assess the potential of Tianjin's urban-scale solar bus parking lots. According to their findings, the photovoltaic bus parking lot's first-year energy generation of 53971.96 MWh was

sufficient to support 50% of the buses' regular operations. The energy-related aspects of installing solar photovoltaic (PV)-powered electric vehicle (EV) charging stations on large-scale merchants' parking infrastructure were examined [13]. According to a case study, each Wal-Mart Supercenter in the US has the ability to generate 3.1 MW of solar electricity, which could power about 100 EV charging stations. About 90% of Americans live within 15 miles of a Wal-Mart, and the company may install 11.1 GW of solar canopies over its Supercenter parking lots to provide over 346,000 EV charging stations powered by solar energy for its patrons. In another study [14], the possibilities of this solution was examined, beginning with a brief synopsis of the financial, environmental, and technical barriers to the construction of solar parking lots. The design of photovoltaic (PV) systems for a passenger car parking garage's roof plane is the subject of another article [15]. The PV system type that was chosen is optimized for the highest possible level of electricity production efficiency.

On the outskirts of Žilina, a parking house model solution was built. On the basis of solar technology and parking lots, a solar parking lot was created. The solar parking lot system comprises; Four 60W solar panels (with a maximum power of 240W), 150Ah rechargeable battery, 1kVA inverter, 12V charging controller, light detecting resistor (LDR) sensor, galvanized steel pipes, and a wooden roof structure [16]. The inverter's output power (actual power = 800W), open circuit voltage (V_{oc}), and minimum peak power (P_{mpp}) are 22V and 57W, respectively. The solar panels also serve as a roof to provide shade.

However, the creation of solar parking lots with smart management systems is a game-changer in this area since it offers the best way to locate an electric vehicle charging station and create internet of things (IoT)-based parking spaces[17]. This essay presents the idea of eco-parking platforms and talks about how cities may use them. The findings of this study can help businesses and urban planners decide how to carry out this project and accomplish sustainable transportation.

In a study that presented a photovoltaic-powered smart parking prototype[18], the main objectives were to construct an ultrasonic parking sensor circuit to alert drivers of any obstructions when parking, determine the power rating and size of PV panels suitable for smart vehicle parking systems, and create a PV-powered smart car parking prototype.

A Smart parking consists of an Arduino UNO potentiometer, resistors, LEDs, distance sensors, and a Node MCU. At the Admiralty University of Nigeria in Delta State, a 3.5kW solar carport for staff quarter lighting and vehicle shade has been investigated [19]. The staff quarter's illumination consumes 120 kWh of electricity, according the energy audit. In addition to UV-induced deterioration, cars exposed to the atmosphere without shade are susceptible to oxidative, thermal, and atmospheric deterioration. Life Cycle Cost (LCC) for establishing a 3.5kW solar photovoltaic parking lot over a seven-year period is 11,088\$, while the LCC for running a 3.5kW (4.38KVA) system is \$14,336.

As a part of the Public and Municipal Renewable Energy Project, a case study of a solar carport; intended to be installed in one of Kocaeli University faculties, was designed and simulated using PV*SOL software [20]. An estimated 55 MWh of power will be produced yearly by the proposed 49 kWp solar (PV) system, generating a total income or savings of 183,967€. Over the course of seven years, it is anticipated to save 25,844 kg of CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere and cut yearly energy costs by 99%, totaling \$11,088:00. In another study a solar carport that was installed at Tarbiat Modares University, at Tehran's Faculty of Agriculture and connected to the electricity grid [21]. The parking lot produced 48.2 MWh of electricity annually, had an annual power factor of 0.791, and 499.89 tons reduction of CO₂ emissions over a 30-year period.

A sizing assessment of a grid-connected solar parking system was presented in a research submitted by Dahbi et al[22]. This system is situated in the southwest Algerian area of Adrar. Photovoltaic panels, cables, and converters are the system components. Analytical

methods have been used to model and size each of these components. PVSYST software is used to simulate and validate the suggested approach. Another article[23] includes a study of the viability and efficiency of utilizing such a system to charge electric vehicles owned by Applied Science Private University staff and students, as well as a basic design for an off-grid PV-covered carport. In order to enable students and staff to charge their electric vehicles from an off-grid carport system while on campus, the study is based on real solar irradiance data that was gathered on-site during university business hours (8 a.m.–5 p.m.). The integration of a solar carport canopy with a possible EV charging station was examined in another study [24] under a range of operational circumstances. The carport in Kaohsiung City, southern Taiwan, has been thoroughly examined. Topics covered include electricity generation, the effects of emissions, and the financial analysis of the solar EV charging station. According to a case study's findings, a potential 140 MWh/year solar energy yield could power over 3000 cars each month with a one-hour parking period, producing 94% fewer carbon dioxide emissions overall than electricity generated using conventional grid methods.

A Solar Carport equipped with repurposed EV batteries is installed at Óbuda University campus[6]. The system comprises solar PV panels, inverter, EV batteries, EV chargers, and a battery management unit (BMS). The Solar Carport may be remotely operated by the citywide micro-grid. The installation of solar parking canopies at the Nikola Tesla Niš parking lot at Electrical Engineering High School was examined by Pantić[25] using PVsyst program. According to simulations, solar system yields a 91.9% ROI during an 8.4-year payback period.

Dayera & Palungan analyzed the feasibility of a PV solar parking system in Multimedia Nusantara University's (UMN) [26]. The study evaluated the performance of the suggested system using PVSyst simulation. According to the simulation results, the system generates 224 MWh of electricity per year, which would cover 20% of UMN's buildings A and D's energy requirements. The required first investment is Rp 781,883,953.26 and according to the financial analysis the system is sustainable with a NPV of Rp 4,380,435,791 and an IRR of 34.28%. Furthermore, it is projected that installing this system will result in a 2775.513-ton reduction in carbon emissions. A solar electric car driving range can be increased by parking it in the sun, which will assist charge its battery [27]. In order to investigate the vehicle's thermal performance when parked in the sun, the thermal characteristics of a passenger car during normal summertime conditions in a moderate latitude temperate locale is described (Lisbon, Portugal) [28]. The critical parking period, below which the parking session does not contribute to net charging, is approximately two hours for the particular conditions evaluated and a 0.5 kWp PV system.

In order to install low and medium power solar systems and produce electricity, the current study suggests making the most use of the space that is available on parking space canopies in urban locations. An on-grid carport is used in this work to present a comprehensive techno-economic model based on the unique peculiarities of Egypt. Energy distribution, availability of renewable energy, living expenses, energy prices, future mobility, and present and projected electrical power scenarios form the basis of this model. There is no prior research that addresses these limitations in Egypt while providing a comprehensive outlook on the country's energy and transportation future. If the concept for this project is expanded to other factories and government buildings, it is anticipated that the planned work will show effectiveness at the national level. The authors selected the New Valley in Egypt as the site for the presented solar PV parking project. Both wall chargers would be rated at 1142 kWp, which is the nominal power. This article discusses the possibilities of using the Eco-parking platform to address parking management and lists the primary obstacles that could hinder the system's effectiveness. The findings of this study can help businesses and urban planners carry out this initiative in a way that promotes sustainable transportation. The structure of this paper is as follows: The third section covers temperature and sunlight data collection. In addition to the simulation program software utilized in Egypt with PVsyst, the fourth section is the methodology that provides the modeling of every component of

the solar parking system. The fifth section presents the results of system simulation and the discussion. Section six provides the conclusion.

3. Data Collection

3.1 Location

The parking location is in New Valley Governorate, Egypt and the coordinates; latitude of $24^{\circ}94'N$ and longitude of $28^{\circ}61'E$. Since obstacles and shading lower the quantity of power generated by solar panels, shading and light obstructions can be a serious problem. Trees, weather, and sounding building structures are the most common sources of shade. However, as shown in Figure 9, the parking lot has the benefit of being a clear, open space in this work analysis.

Fig.9: Parking space area

3.2 Resource data

Determining the site's suitability for solar radiation is crucial for using solar PV for commercial, residential, and agricultural purposes. This requires determining the best location and orientation for the panels, taking into account the maximum amount of sunlight received. Solar statistics are derived from the monthly average of observations in the New Valley region from 2021 to 2024. Figure 10 shows the site's temperature resources, while Figure 11 demonstrates the solar resource profile (monthly average radiation) of the selected site. Information on the sun's direction throughout the year and the quantity of sunlight gathered at the garage is provided by the radiation rate and time window.

3.3 Load summary

The monthly average bill of consumption is 480,000 L.E with total in year of 5 Million L.E. So, the required proposed solar plant doesn't larger than 1.24 MWp.

Fig.10: Monthly average temperature data of New Valley

Fig.11: Monthly average solar radiation data of New Valley

4. Methodology

4.1 Modeling of solar garage parking system

The PV system's size is determined by a number of factors, namely the sites potential and the energy needed. The following is an estimate of the daily energy production[22]:

$$E_c = P \times Q \times h \quad (1)$$

Where: E_c : Consumed energy (Wh / day), P : Electrical power (W), Q : Number of the used panels and h : Time (hour). The site irradiation determines the peak power of the panels needed for installation. The following formula is used to compute it[29]:

$$P_c = \frac{E_c}{KIr} = \frac{E_p}{Ir} \quad (2)$$

Since; P_c : Peak power in peak watts (Wc) and I_r : Average annual daily irradiation (kWh / m².j). The total number of the installed PV modules is calculated by

$$N = \frac{P_c}{P_u} \quad (3)$$

P_u : unit peak power of the modules watts (W) and the number of the serial PV modules is given by:

$$N_s = \frac{U_{ond}}{U_{mod}} \quad (4)$$

U_{ond} is the input voltage at the terminals of the inverter and U_{mod} is the unit voltage of the modules. The number of the parallel PV modules is calculated by:

$$N_p = \frac{P_c}{N_s \times P_{mod}} \quad (5)$$

P_{mod} is the peak power of the PV module.

Using wires that are capable of supporting both DC and AC current is crucial. A properly sized cable section can accomplish this. Additionally, both the ambient temperature and the temperature brought on by Joule losses must be supported by the isolation. It is necessary to identify the cable segments that have the lowest potential voltage loss between the panels and the inverter/charger and between the batteries and the same device. The voltage drop can't be more than 3% [22]. The cable section can be obtained by using the following equation:

$$R = \frac{\Delta U}{I} \quad (6)$$

ΔU : maximum voltage drop in the cable; I : current circulating in the cable and R : cable resistance. In order for the inverter power (P_{ond}) and boost power (P_{reg}) to exceed the peak power (P_c), it is important that:

$$P_{reg} \geq P_c \quad (7)$$

$$P_{ond} \geq P_c \quad (8)$$

This model is applied to a solar parking lot using the aforementioned equations.

4.2 Simulation of the solar parking in in New Valley

The identical solar parking system will be shown and simulated using PV system software. The outcomes of the simulation will then be evaluated. PVSYST is used in this section to simulate solar parking that is connected to the grid. PVSYST is useful software that allows simulating and verifying projects [30]. It imports weather and geographically data to give results very closer to the real case. Furthermore, it can do a good sizing of the system and its production estimation with optimization. The required power production of the 1142 kWp on-grid solar PV system is calculated to match the load requirements using the PVSyst simulation program, which is used in this study. There are multiple sources from which climate and meteorological data can be imported. Additionally, it uses a variety of information from the hourly simulation to forecast simulated system yields. The simulation study will follow the following protocol: tools for calculating the output of solar power plants, whether they are connected to the grid. The PVSYST system sizing process involves a number of processes, including localization setup, PV kind, inverter sort, output power, load type, etc. the proposed scheme system is shown in figure 12. An azimuth of 0.13° , or south, tilt angle of 21.8° and a slope of 334 m are employed as shown in figure 13. Following that, the kind of inverter and solar panel to be used are chosen. Next, the 18816 m² area designated for solar panel installation is entered as illustrated in figure 14. Lastly,

the installation site of the solar system, its system, and all things that could throw shadows are all modeled in three dimensions. The 3D model of the PV module with steel structure is shown in figure 15.

Fig.12: Proposed system scheme

Fig. 13: Position of PV modules used

Fig.14: Position of PV array with the given area

Fig.15: 3D model of PV module with steel structure

5. Results and Discussion

The single line diagram of the proposed system is presented in figure 16. Setting the localization, PV type, inverter sort, output power, and load type are just a few of the many stages that go into system sizing with PVSYST. The solar parking is made up of 1872 PV modules (Jinko solar) with 760 V and 1390 A, according to the results of the analysis and simulation. Each of the 18 PVs (610 Wp per one) should be connected in serial to raise the voltage, and the 104 groups of 18 PVs are connected in parallel (26 string) to raise the current. These groups are connected to the grid by means of three boosts and eight inverters, and their combined power is 924 kWac. The total power of this proposed plant is 1142 kWp. The bill of quantities of this proposed system is shown in table 1. Figure 17 displays an iso-shadings diagram for our location that displays the Sun's path for significant dates throughout the year in addition to shading losses, which are evidently greatest in the winter.

Fig.16: Single line diagram of the car park connected to the grid

Table 1: Bill of quantities of proposed system

Item	Quantity
PV moduels Jinko 610 Wp	2016
Inverter Huawei 115 KVA	8
DC cables 6 mm (m)	14 km
MC4 clamp	150
LV 800 A DB	2
CB 800 A MCCB	4
CB 250 A MCCB	8
Ac cables 3*150 + 70 Cu (m)	400
Ac cables 3*70 + 35 Cu (m)	500
Earth cable 6 mm Cu (m)	200
Earth cable 10 mm Cu (m)	900
Earth cable 35 mm Cu (m)	500
Earth cable 70 mm Cu (m)	400
Earth PIT (MWp)	1.12
RS 485	500
Weather station	1
Data Logger	1
Mounting structure (MWp)	1.12
Bracket (18 columns *2 Rows) Portrait orientation	56
LV trench 1m * 0.5 m	260
DC trench 1m * 0.5 m	300
Earthling trench 2m * 0.5 m	260

Fig.17: Iso-shadings diagram

The shade that the solar panels covering the cars produce is one of the obvious advantages of the solar parking canopy. Shade significantly lowers the vehicle's daytime temperature and shields it from sun damage, including warped interiors and cracked or damaged paintwork during the sweltering summer months. In the spring and summer, an automobile in a normal parking lot is exposed to direct sunshine. The temperature inside a car can rapidly rise from 37°C to 54°C if the outside temperature reaches 27°C or higher, according to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. The energy consumption would rise from 2% to 70% at 35°C, and the additional energy needed to operate the air conditioning system would be the cause of these increases. The type of air conditioning system, engine architecture, power terrain capabilities, and drive patterns all affected these energy consumption increases. The impact of climate control (heating or cooling) on energy usage increases with power terrain efficiency. The Normalized productions (per installed kWp) of this proposed system is exhibited in figure 18.

Fig.18: Normalized productions (per installed kWp)

The annual produced energy from this proposed system is 2211.04 MWh while the apparent energy is 2329.46 MWh/year. The specific production is 1936 kWh/kWp/year. The main results of energy produced and energy injected to grid is shown in table 2. The average monthly performance ration

of this system is 84% as shown in figure 19. Power output distribution of this proposed system is illustrated in figure 20 while Figure 21 is exhibited daily Input/output diagram of this system.

Table 2: Basic main results of energy for proposed system

	GlobHor kWh/m ²	DiffHor kWh/m ²	T_Amb °C	GlobInc kWh/m ²	GlobEff kWh/m ²	EArray MWh	E_Grid MWh	PR ratio
January	128.5	38.56	12.31	170.1	163.0	174.5	169.0	0.870
February	138.3	47.95	14.65	169.0	162.4	172.8	167.3	0.867
March	183.7	64.06	19.24	204.5	196.2	204.5	198.0	0.848
April	197.9	79.49	23.91	202.2	193.5	199.7	193.6	0.838
May	215.7	87.56	28.21	205.6	196.3	201.0	195.0	0.831
June	220.3	81.00	30.81	203.4	194.0	197.7	191.8	0.826
July	223.1	79.16	32.00	208.4	198.7	201.2	195.2	0.820
August	210.5	80.76	31.98	208.7	199.4	201.0	195.0	0.818
September	186.4	60.43	29.01	200.5	192.0	192.8	186.9	0.816
October	165.1	53.59	25.07	195.0	187.6	192.3	186.3	0.837
November	134.6	37.85	18.46	175.1	168.2	176.7	171.1	0.856
December	119.8	39.35	14.09	162.6	155.7	166.9	161.8	0.871
Year	2123.9	749.75	23.36	2305.1	2207.1	2281.0	2211.0	0.840

Legends

- GlobHor Global horizontal irradiation
- DiffHor Horizontal diffuse irradiation
- T_Amb Ambient Temperature
- GlobInc Global incident in coll. plane
- GlobEff Effective Global, corr. for IAM and shadings
- EArray Effective energy at the output of the array
- E_Grid Energy injected into grid
- PR Performance Ratio

Fig.19: Performance ration curve of proposed system

Fig.20: System Output Power Distribution

Fig.21: Daily Input/output diagram

The loss diagram of this proposed system is shown in figure 22. The total cost of this proposed system is 502,480 USD and cost of energy per kwh is system is 0.0227 USD. The total CO₂ emissions avoided against this proposed system at the end of 25 years' project system lifetime is 24379.16 ton as shown in figure 23 and table 3. The grid lifecycle emissions are 458gCO₂/kwh. Table 4 illustrated system lifecycle emissions details.

Fig. 22: Loss diagram

Fig. 22: Loss diagram

Fig.23: Saved CO₂ Emission vs. system life time

Table 3: System Lifecycle Emissions Details

Item	LCE	Quantity	Subtotal
			[kgCO ₂]
Modules	951 kgCO ₂ /modules	2016 modules	1916264
Supports	3.05 kgCO ₂ /kg	20160 kg	61586
Inverters	303 kgCO ₂ /units	8.00 units	2421

6. Conclusions

Based on the design and simulation of a grid-connected photovoltaic parking lot in New Valley Governorate, Egypt using PVsyst software, the best side angle for installing the power plant's photovoltaic modules was found to be 21.8 degrees using the method of maximizing annual production. The crystal module is of the Jinko JKM-610N-78HL4-BDV brand and has a 610 watt rated power. There are 1872 PV modules with 760 V and 1390 A in the solar parking. Each of the 18 PVs (610 Wp each) should be connected in series to increase the voltage, while the 104 groups (26 string) of 18 PVs are connected in parallel to increase the current. Eight inverters and three boosters connect these groups to the grid, and their aggregate output is 924 kWac. The total power of this proposed facility is 1142 kWp. Eight SMA solar inverters; German-made, of SUN2000-115KTL-M2-400V type, manufactured in 2014, with power of 115 kW was selected. Based on the location of the modules, the shading loss in the parking lot was estimated to be 28.6% per year.

The amount of energy fed into the grid was calculated to be 2211.5 megawatt hours per year. The specific production is 1936 kWh/kWp/year. The average monthly performance rate of this system is 84%. The total cost of this proposed system is 502,480 USD and cost of energy per kWh is system is 0.0227 USD. If this solar parking lot is built, in addition to using clean energy, it is predicted that 24379.16 tons of carbon dioxide will be released into the atmosphere in 30 years. The return of investment is less than 7 years, after which it becomes profitable.

The long-term performance of such systems in various climates, the incorporation of battery storage for improved energy management, and the approach's possible scalability in various metropolitan environments should all be investigated in future studies. To optimize the uptake and influence of solar parking canopies in building resilient and energy-efficient communities, cooperation with legislators and urban planners is essential.

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